

**A STUDY ON ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN
DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING
COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR**

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Abstract:

The Project Report Entitled as "A Study on Organisation Culture in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur". The organizational culture is the powerful tools that have tremendous effect on the morale, performance and job satisfaction in the organization. The organizational culture is the set of important perceptions, notions and behaviors that the members of the community share in common. It consists of a basic set of values, ideas, preferences and ethics, code of conduct, principles and beliefs, reinforced by logical expectations and assumptions as well as responsive attitudes and ethical norms which create distinctiveness among human groups. It is a manifestation of the attitudes of organizational members towards the organization.

Key Words: Organization Culture, Awareness of Program, Working of Organization.

Introduction:

The importance of this study is to review on how organizational culture can affect the behavior of faculty in the organization. After the finding in this research work, the result will be used to improve the current practice in organization in regards to how culture affects its faculty behavior of the Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College will know how best to use its organizational culture to improve better.

Meaning Organization:

Organization is an entity comprising multiple people, such as an institution or an association that has collective goal and is linked to an external environment. The word is derived from the Greek word oraganon which means "organ".

Culture:

Culture is the characteristics and know ledge of a particular group of people, encompassing language, religion, cuisine, social habits, music and arts. The word "culture" derives" from a French term, which in turn derives from the Latin "Colere" Which means to tend to earth and grow, or cultivation and nature.

Review of Literature:

Denison (1984), argue that the perception regarding organization members participation and involvement indicate both the existing and future organization financial performance. Research about managerial level practices and values organize by the French theorists align with the pattern of escalation and growth.

Robbins (1986), on the other hand, defines organizational culture as a uniform perception of the organization which has common characteristics. Organizational culture, according to the author is something descriptive and effectively it can distinguish one particular organization from another. It can also integrate individuals and groups of organization systems.

Deshpande and Wesbter (1989), define organizational culture as "the pattern of shared values and beliefs that help individuals understand organizational functioning and thus provide them with norms for behavior in the organization"

Schein (1990), demonstrate that the studies regarding the firm's culture must adopt the methodological way in order to assist the scholars and management professionals to recognize and apply all the antecedents and variables appropriate for the empirical investigation.

Cameron and Quinn (1999), suggest organizational culture refers to the taken-for-granted values the underlying assumptions, expectations, collective memories, and definitions present in the organization. It represents how things are around here. It reflects the prevailing ideology that people carry inside their heads. It conveys a sense of identity and provides unspoken guidelines for how to get along and enhances the stability of the social system to which they belong.

Rousseau (2000), as a set of commonly experienced stable characteristics of an organization which shows the distinctive features of an organization which differentiates it from others. Similar to the definitions of Ahzar (2003) that has been stated above, Rousseau (2000) and group across the organization. Organizational values and beliefs refer to the common ideas about what the shared goals of an organization are, what types of behavior should the members of an organization follow in order to active the common goals of an organization

Hofstede (2006), in order to understand the full complexity of organizational culture, a number of researches made attempts to recognize and examine the components of the organizational culture. One of the inseparable components of the organizational culture is the values that are shared and held by the individuals of an organization on the other hand explains the organizational culture in the form of onion that contains a number of layers and values that make the core of the organizational culture.

Objectives of the Study:

- A study on organizational culture in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.
- To study the impact of organizational culture in work environment.
- To analyze the diversity culture management in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering college.
- To study an organizational culture adopt in an organization.

Research Methodology:

Research is the process of systematic and in depth study or search of any particular topic, subject or area of investigation, backed by collection, compilation, Presentation and interpretation of relevant details or data. It is careful search or find out valuation facts, which would be useful for further application or utilization.

Research Design:

The researcher used Descriptive Research Design. Descriptive Research design means fact finding one. The Research used this research design to find out the fact of respondents attitude and opinion about student empowerment.

Sampling Design:

The Sampling type is Simple Random Sample which involves deliberating selection of particular units constituting a sample, which represents the universe, is used for conducting the study.

Sample Size:

Sample size denotes the number of sample selected for the study. They sample size for this study is fixed at 120respondents.

Data Collection Method:

Data are the basic input to any decision making processing of data gives statistics of importance of study.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Limitation of the Study:

- As opinions are dynamic the results of the study based on these opinions are likely to differ in future.
- The result also depends on the integrity of the respondents in giving true and fair opinions and their level of knowledge in subject under study.
- The study also inherits all the limitations of the sampling technique used for conducting the survey.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Relationship between the satisfaction level of working hours of the organization and number of hours in the time table.

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Highly Satisfied	32	29.09
2	Satisfied	52	47.27
3	Moderate	24	21.81
4	Dissatisfied	2	1.81
5	Highly Dissatisfied	-	-
	Total	110	100

Source: Primary Data

Chart:

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 29.09 % of respondents highly satisfied with the number of hours in the time table, 47.27 % of respondents Satisfied with the number of hours in the time table, 21.81% of respondents

moderate with the number of hours in the time table, 1.81 % of respondents dissatisfied with the number of hours in the time table.

Correlation:

Satisfaction level of working hours of the organization (X)	31	68	8	3	0	110
Satisfaction level of number of hours in the time table (Y)	32	52	24	2	0	110

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
31	32	961	1024	992
68	52	4624	2704	3536
8	24	64	576	192
3	2	9	4	6
0	0	0	0	0
$\sum X=110$	$\sum Y=110$	$\sum X^2=5658$	$\sum Y^2=4308$	$\sum XY=4726$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{n(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2} \cdot \sqrt{n(\sum Y^2) - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

Answer:

$$r_{xy} = 0.9328$$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between satisfaction level of working hours in the organization and number of hours in the time table.

Suggestions:

Since the organization is perceived to be effective, and since most of the respondents have positive feelings about it, the management should take care to maintain the current way of working .It might however help to look into the reasons behind some of the employees experiencing stress as well as insecurity. Information regarding the work should reach in time.

Conclusion:

The respondents' attitudes towards their jobs are positive with a majority of the respondents agreeing that there has been an improvement in their attitudes in the recent past. Among the reasons for this positive improvement are the following: the work has become more interesting their jobs. With regard to the organization, a vast majority of the respondents have the strong sense of belonging, and they take pride in working for the organization. Most of them feel comfortable working here.

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